

D4.5 – Dissemination and Communication Final Report

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D4.5 Dissemination and Communication Final Report

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Abstract

Communication and dissemination are key elements of BIMprove project. Since the beginning of its implementation, the partners have carried out an outstanding impact strategy that has brought interesting results, enabling the project to highlight and disseminate its outcomes with the community of practice built. In this final report, BIMprove showcases the set of actions developed (branding strategy, website and social networks daily updates, participation at events, publications and articles, generation of multimedia material, stakeholder collaboration, among others) leading to the great impact of the project achieved.

Keywords

Outreach material, dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement, impact.

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BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that BIMprove system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. INTRODUCTION

It's not a secret that part of the success of an innovation depends on the awareness about this innovation. Through an effective dissemination and communication strategy, the project and its results can gain widespread attention. Therefore, a solid dissemination and communication strategy ensures the involvement of relevant stakeholders in the project and can offer opportunities for future development.

The current deliverable provides an overview of all key activities and actions related to communication and dissemination that took place during the whole project implementation. It gives an analytic presentation of the performance of our digital channels, our participation in physical and online events, our scientific publications, online articles, impact of our communication campaigns, multimedia material generated, etc.

The basis of this document are both [D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan](#) that set the foundations of our strategy and [D4.3 Dissemination and Communication Interim Report](#), that showcased the activities implemented during the first 18 months of the project. One thing is clear, communication and dissemination needs to be agile and ready to adapt according to the needs of the project and the overall environment. Therefore, within this report we explain how, besides keeping the implementation of the Dissemination and Communication strategy on track, we have implemented activities ahead of time as we found the opportunity and the right time.

In addition, this deliverable provides an overview and criticism of our unique Agile Stakeholder Management Strategy, an open framework of collaboration with peers and groups that can benefit and contribute to the overall impact of the project. We reveal some key activities and interactions that took place during our 3 Sprints and highlight the key lessons learnt we extracted from this experience.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

BIMprove partners have devoted significant efforts into communicating and disseminating critical project activities, outcomes and findings to the wider community. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the performance of **BIMprove’s Dissemination & Communication Strategy** as defined in [D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan](#) and as a continuation of [D4.3 Dissemination and Communication Interim Report](#), while presenting all key activities that took place during the project life.

2.1. Overview on the Dissemination strategy and performance

Throughout this first 18-month period, communication and dissemination played a significant and crucial role to **BIMprove’s** overall workplan and performance. Although both activities are quite interlinked, in **BIMprove** we chose to treat them as different but closely depended to each other. Our primary focus has been given into defining the appropriate channels and paths for better reach of our audience and target groups while continuously evaluating and adjusting our strategies and activities based on the response that we had and the outcomes that project produced.

Figure 1: Communication & Dissemination Strategy M1-M18

	M1	M6	M12	M18
Dissemination	Phase 1: Analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse BIMprove's Framework Define priorities & actions Identify key stakeholders Develop 1st set of promotional material 		Phase 2: Increase Impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapt measures channels identified Match means to target groups & stakeholders Participate in workshops, events, etc. Revisit Strategy Upgrade-Update promotional material 	
Communication	Plan & Revisit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan activities Prepare/Setup tools and measure for communication Scout for potential key targets and stakeholders Revisit plan and apply mitigations measures if needed 		Early bird Communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early Communication about the project and foreseen activities Articles to communicate our project to a wide audience Develop additional communication material (i.e. brochures) Participation in online events for networking reasons 	

Throughout the second half of the project (M18-36), the Dissemination and Communication Strategy was redefined to adapt it to the new wave of implementation activities and. Knowing our target audience and having a wider community allowed us to develop a more targeted communication and to move to a new phase where to leverage project awareness, evaluate the outcomes, refine priorities and boost the visibility and impact of BIMprove.

Figure 2: Communication & Dissemination Strategy M18-36

2.1.1. Dissemination Strategy Assessment

While during the first half of the project emphasis has been given mainly to communication related activities, during the second half we have been able to release a more solid and mature scientific and technological related outcomes of the project. Thanks to the number of preliminary activities implemented not only to set up the ground and instruments, we achieved a stable dissemination outreach that has been easily maintained by the project partners actively involved in multiple hands-on activities, research publications and participation in scientific related events.

2.1.1.1 Phase I - Analysis

In this preliminary phase that started at M01, the consortium analysed and noted down means (i.e. scientific journals, publications, key visuals, etc.) and events, related to the project's scientific

domains, which we will have to tackle in order to achieve a meaningful and realistic dissemination impact. The results of Phase 1 have been included in [D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan](#).

2.1.1.2 Phase II - Increase impact

The main objective of Phase II, which started at M06, was to increase impact and awareness generated during Phase I and to expose the main **BIMprove** achievements. Another key objective was to start building relationships and interactions with the community to prepare them for the adoption of our outcomes in a later stage. During this first project period, the consortium has started building relationships with key initiatives by signing MoUs, participate in events and bilateral discussion in order to prepare the ground for the next phase. Synergies with exploitation and standardisation activities are also crucial.

2.1.1.3 Phase III - Adoption

This phase, which started at M18, has leveraged the general awareness raised in Phase I and Phase II, attracting more potential users, customers and adopters of **BIMprove** project's results. In this phase we counted on more mature outcomes to present and display. The ultimate goal has been to diffuse our knowledge and outcomes into other initiatives, through dedicated activities (i.e. scientific journals, conferences, white papers, presentations, etc.). As above, synergies with exploitation and standardisation activities have been of great importance.

2.2. Overview on the Communication strategy and performance

2.2.1. Communication Strategy Assessment

In this section, we are sharing the different communication resources into implementing activities around the three phases of the strategy: a) Plan and Revisit, b) Early Bird Communication and c) Targeted Communication).

2.2.1.1 Plan and revisit

The first communication phase started at M1 of the project and primarily aimed at planning all activities, setting up the main communication tools and channels (Website, Social Media, etc), and identified potential target groups and stakeholders. The result of this phase was the creation of our communication strategy (as reported in [D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan](#)), the development of a number of communication tools (including printed material as described in [D4.2 Outreach Material](#)) and the continuous update of our Stakeholders Database, an internal mindmap which is used to map our primary target groups (stakeholders). This phase lasted until the end of the project and included the revisiting of our Database, the modification of existing printed material, tools and overall strategy based on project needs.

2.2.1.2 *Early bird Communication*

The second phase started at M6, even though some minor activities have started earlier. During this phase, early bird communication activities took place aiming to communicate both to a wider public and to specific communities, the existence of the project as an instance and its forthcoming activities and actions. Emphasis has been given to the online tools and measures, as they tend to have a wider reach than traditional measures. During this phase, participation for networking purposes to webinars or other online events and publication of articles over the internet about the project took place. This phase will also last for the whole duration of the project as it mainly focuses on communicating the generic aspect of the project to a wide stakeholder base.

2.2.1.3 *Targeted Communication*

The third communication phase started in M18 and focused on a more advanced communication and dissemination content linked to more concrete activities and outcomes. It has been possible to develop targeted communication activities such as producing and communicating articles, blogs or posts specifically on certain project outcomes and benefits, hosting and/or participating in online events (or physical if possible) for the communication of **BIMprove's** innovations, production of targeted communication material (i.e. videos) for the community, etc

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES IMPLEMENTED

During the 36-month period, **BIMprove** has implemented a large number of communication and dissemination activities. While some of them clearly belong to one segment or another (communication or dissemination), a significant proportion of them belong to both segments as they serve a two-fold purpose.

In this section, we mention all the dissemination and communication activities implemented based on the different categories included in the following graph.

Figure 3: Dissemination and Communication categories

3.1. Online channels

Nowadays, digital tools are the backbone of communication between an initiative and its target audience. **BIMprove** has devoted significant efforts towards its digital tools, especially social media, not only for exposing its outcomes to the target groups, but also **for creating a community around the project** interested in Digital Twins, Technology and Construction therefore establishing **BIMprove** as a “**recognised**” brand where people can visit or follow to find out news about these domains.

Establishing BIMprove as a brand and building a community of followers around at the beginning of the project, it gave us the opportunity to capitalise on the second half of the project where dissemination of our results and outcomes has been the major focus.

3.1.1. Project Website

[BIMprove website](#) is our main gateway. It includes all relevant information about the project and news related to our activities.

Figure 4: BIMprove Website

During the project duration, the website has attracted **4,782 new users** who have generated **7,598 visits** while viewed over **16,367 pages**. The average engagement duration is 1 min 32 s. The reporting date is 15 August 2023.

Given the nature of our project and the limited audience who might be interested to what we do, the metrics are more than acceptable.

During the last months, we have made an effort updating the website content in order to include the latest outcomes and results. Therefore, two new sections have been created in the website:

- **Gallery:** which includes a set of videos outstanding the impact of the project. In this section we have included interviews done to project partners as well as the final milestone with the video presentation at BIM World.
- **Markers:** which contains text, video, pictures and download material regarding the work developed by the project preparing a CEN workshop agreement: “Position markers for digital applications on construction sites, structural monitoring and BIM-applications”.

3.1.2. Social Media

BIMprove’s Social Media accounts are the backbone of our everyday communication. Both our Social Media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn) have reached **3,119 followers** and a monthly average of almost **6,000 impressions**. The reporting date is 15 August 2023.

TWITTER	LINKEDIN
2,407 followers	713 followers

Despite the fact that the Twitter account has a larger number of followers and the community there was easier to make it grow, in LinkedIn we have experienced a higher engagement and impact, meaning a more trustful and committed audience. Regarding LinkedIn, we would like to highlight the following metrics for the last year of activity (August 2022 – August 2023).

Number of impressions		68,883
Number of monthly average impressions		5,740
Total Engagement (4,080)	Clicks	1,833
	Reactions	2,122
	Comments	56
	Reposts	69
Engagement rate		5,7%
Number of posts		321

Twitter and LinkedIn have been the most exploited channels to communicate and disseminate the project implementation and outcomes. On a monthly basis, AUSTRALO, the Communication and Dissemination Leader has prepared an editorial calendar, planning all contents and publications. We have based our activity on social media campaign delivery. Some of the campaigns launched the last year of the project have been:

Project' achievements	Pilot Use Case implementation	Industry News
Sharing project meetings, publication of new articles,	Sharing the technical progress and the implementation of the BIMprove pilot use cases.	Sharing news from the construction industry addressing topics related to the project

<p>deliverables, participation in events, etc.</p>		
<p>Team recognition</p>	<p>Impact Interviews</p>	<p>Results Campaign</p>
<p>Social media posts recognising the work of the main team members of the project</p>	<p>Sharing interviews done to project team members about the impact generated by BIMprove</p>	<p>Facing the last months of the project, this campaign aims at sharing the main results of the project</p>

3.1.3. YouTube Channel

Since M10, we have created our [YouTube Channel](#) that we used to upload and shared our own videos of our demonstration technologies. We have created and shared **31 videos** that have attracted **3,651 views** so far. Many of our videos are also available on our website. The reporting date is 15 August 2023, and the number of views is expected to increase until the official end day of the project and more in the years to come.

Table 1: YouTube Public Videos

Videos	Views
Augmented Reality (AR) visualisation of BIM Model	567
Multi-User Virtual Reality	187
Ground Robot BIMprove system integration and operation	152
Leica BLK 360 Point-clouds scans	248
Data-capturing drones	109
Detection of safety structures and untidy places in images	105
Mapping point clouds to IFC-elements	288
BIM@Vehicle: First Version of the UI	176
Schedule import and view	86
Revision change visualisation	145
PUC visit Madrid	57
BIMprove XR-Viewer: MultiXR (Multi-User - Multi-Location - Multi-Device)	122
BIMprove Pilot Use Case Lausanne November 2022 summary video	105
BIMprove 2022 wrap-up: a year of achievements	44
Women in BIMprove: Caroline Cheng	21
Women in BIMprove: Ingvild B. Småge	15
BIMprove Stuttgart Integration Meeting - March 2023	36
BIMprove presentation at the BIM World Paris 2023 by Wojciech Teclaw	36
Impact Interviews: Johannes Brozovsky, Researcher at SINTEF Community	75
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3.1.4. Online Repository (ZENODO)

BIMprove project has been respecting and supporting the **Open Access principle** from day one. Open Access helps other projects and initiatives to build upon previous research results, improving their overall quality, encourages collaboration while avoiding duplication and the wasting of resources. It speeds up innovation, and faster progress in the market translates to faster growth. Lastly, everyone in the society is involved, which brings about more transparency of the scientific process.

For that reason, we have been using **BIMprove's Open Access Repository** through **ZENODO**, the **OpenAIRE** repository hosted by **CERN**. Our online repository has a total of 56 documents, **3,626 unique online views** and **2,691 downloads** of our public documents. The reporting date is 15 August 2023, and the number of views and downloads is expected to increase until the official end day of the project and more in the years to come.

Table 2: BIMprove's Open Access Repository

Category	Document	Year	Views	Downloads
Newsletter	BIMprove 7th Newsletter	2023	8	15
Deliverable	D3.6–Benchmarking, Evaluation & Demonstration	2023	12	7
Publication	Ontologies in digital twin: Methodology, lessons learned and practical approach	2023	35	37
Deliverable	D1.3 – Concept descriptions of user interfaces and humanrobot interaction	2023	123	99
Publication	Deep Learning Machine Vision Solutions for Monitoring Safety Structures to Supplement Building Information Models	2023	155	21

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Newsletter	BIMprove 6th Newsletter	2023	7	19
Publication	Choosing between remote and face-to-face features in a test setting: methodology used in two usability and user experience case studies	2023	60	24
Deliverable	D3.4 - Prototype system description and test results	2023	23	35
Deliverable	D2.7 - User interface software and interface description	2023	27	33
Deliverable	D2.9 - White paper on BIMprove open layer services software and data structure	2023	40	34
Newsletter	BIMprove 5th Newsletter	2022	18	27
Publication	Ontologies and Digital Building Twins (BIMprove contribution to the SPHERE whitepaper)	2022	68	55
Newsletter	BIMprove 4th Newsletter	2022	50	24
Publication	BIM@SiteOffice: Comparing IFC and point clouds in Multiuser VR – Workflows and Tools	2022	101	59
Publication	BIM digital twin visualization in XR – Novel GUI concept	2022	92	54
Publication	Storing, Maintaining & Updating the Digital Twin	2022	83	41
Publication	Evaluation of BIMprove XR User Interfaces	2022	120	30
Deliverable	D2.3 – Open Interface Description for stationery, ground and UAV based data acquisition systems	2022	103	69
Newsletter	BIMprove 3rd Newsletter	2022	58	36
Deliverable	D3.3 – Proof of concept system description and test results	2022	34	29
Deliverable	D4.4 - Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report	2022	38	18
Deliverable	D4.3 – Dissemination and Communication Interim Report	2022	49	42
Deliverable	D2.5 – Safety-critical situation detection	2022	119	51
Publication	XR Based GUI Concept for BIM Digital Twin Data Visualization	2022	92	50
Newsletter	BIMprove 2nd Newsletter	2022	67	24
Publication	Multi-User-XR for Digital Twin Data in Construction	2022	46	33
Deliverable	D1.7 - Use-Case requirements	2022	84	44
Deliverable	D3.1 - Technology Demonstrations	2022	221	116
Deliverable	D3.2 - Functional samples description and test results	2022	31	28
Deliverable	D2.4 - Detailed description of the safety functionalities and worker notifications	2022	77	68
Deliverable	D2.8 - Layer Services description	2022	72	86
Publication	RASAECO: Requirements Analysis of Software for the AECO Industry (Additional Material)	2021	99	39

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Press Release	LC-008-EEB projects Joint Press Release	2021	113	51
Press Release	LC-008-EEB projects Joint Press Release	2021	38	30
Newsletter	BIMprove 1st Newsletter	2021	39	30
Deliverable	D1.6 – Legal Aspects	2021	30	20
Deliverable	D1.3 – Concept descriptions of user interfaces and humanrobot interaction	2021	123	99
Publication	White Paper on Digital Twins and Data Integration in the AECO Sector	2021	370	237
Deliverable	D1.5: Data Integration Interfaces for Building Industry using BIM and Digital Building Twins	2021	113	178
Publication	OpenAPI 3 specification of BIMprove interfaces	2021	21	6
Deliverable	D1.8 - Risk and safety assessment method	2021	66	39
Press Release	Press Release for MoU signed between StandICT.eu2023 & BIMprove	2021	55	40
Deliverable	D4.2 – Outreach Material	2021	35	26
Visual identity	BIMprove H2020 Trifold Brochure	2021	45	32
Visual identity	BIMprove H2020 Poster	2021	47	31
Visual identity	BIMprove Official Logo and Icon	2021	52	22
Visual identity	BIMprove H2020 Roll Up Banner	2021	55	35
Visual identity	BIMprove Brochure (A4)	2021	63	35
Visual identity	BIMprove Poster (A0)	2021	25	15
Visual identity	BIMprove Trifold Brochure	2021	22	16
Deliverable	D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan	2021	219	257
Publication	BIMprove User Interfaces: Multi-User-XR for Construction	2021	45	41
Press Release	BIMprove Joint Press Release	2021	45	27
Press Release	BIMprove - Joint Press Release (Sep 2020)	2020	76	254
Visual identity	BIMprove Icon	2020	32	1
Visual identity	BIMprove Logo	2020	18	1

3.2. Key Collaborations and Stakeholder Community

3.2.1. BIMprove & LC-008-EEB funded projects

All four **LC-008-EEB** funded projects **BIMprove**, **COGITO**, **ASHVIN** and **BIM2TWIN**, agreed on joining forces for **raising awareness around Digital Building Twins** and its impact in the construction industry. Our primary aim is to share knowledge, experiences and research outcomes with other stakeholders and communities around the EU and beyond, via online communication like webinars, newsletters, social media channels and scientific or technical articles. A full press release is available on our [website](#). This collaboration has led to multiple joint communication initiatives, such as the organisation of a joint workshop at **Sustainable Places Conferences** and the celebration of joint workshops addressing the **exploitation strategies** for each of the projects.

Figure 5: Exploitation workshop celebrated 6 February 2023

3.2.2. BIMprove & StandICT.eu2023 project

BIMprove has signed a MoU with **StandICT.eu2023** project for promoting an open innovation approach in the standardization of Digital Twin Technologies. Driving digital twin technology and digitization in construction and building management is challenging, exciting, but also feasible with Open BIM. For this to succeed we need to speak the same language – and that is standards. The cooperation between **BIMprove** and StandICT is an important milestone to drive and develop this unified language. You can read the full announcement and our press release through our [official website](#).

3.3. Promotional materials

To support all communication and dissemination activities, since the beginning of the project we have created several materials to use both virtually an on-site. This material has been available in the common workspace.

Slide Deck

One pager

Tri-fold brochure

Roll-up banner

Poster

Multimedia material

3.3.1. Slide deck

The slide deck is a PPT presentation that has been used by the team members in meetings, events and conferences to present the project to the audience.

3.3.2. One pager

The one pager is a one-page document that contains an executive summary of the project. It has been an essential material to distribute and make our project known to stakeholders. It contains all the basic information of the project.

See the BIMprove one pager [here](#).

3.3.3. Tri-fold brochure

The tri-fold brochure is also known as the letter fold, a tri folded brochure presented in the same style as a letter in an envelope (hence the name). It's folded in two places and the brochure is divided into three, even rectangular sections. We have printed the tri-fold and distribute it to events and conferences where we have participated.

See the BIMprove tri-fold brochure [here](#).

3.3.4. Roll-up banner

The roll-up banner is a self-supporting advertising display comprising a banner – a wide strip of fabric or other material – with content printed on it and a base into which the banner can be rolled up, making it all easy to carry around. We have used the roll-up banner in every event and conference that we had the opportunity to bring.

See the BIMprove roll-up banner [here](#).

Figure 6: Use of roll-up in a presentation

3.3.5. Poster

The poster is a one-page document designed for printing and post it in project partners offices and event's venue, when possible.

See the BIMprove poster [here](#).

Figure 7: Use of poster in an event venue

3.3.6. Audio-visual material

During the project lifetime, we have created a wide range of videos used to promote the project and disseminate its main achievements. We have also created multiple digital banners to make the social media post more attractive.

3.4. Publications

BIMprove has released a total of **82 publications**, that are included the following main categories:

- Press releases
- Online articles
- Newsletters

- Technical & Scientific (Peer Reviewed) Publications

3.4.1. Press Releases

During the project lifetime, we have published 5 Press Releases, that are listed in Table 2.

3.4.2. Online Articles

Our online articles serve two-way purpose: communicate to our target groups any recent development we have made (and can be publicly announced) and disseminate key knowledge with specific target groups.

In total, we have published in our website 60 articles.

Table 3: Website Articles

Title	Platform
The Digital Twin in BIMprove: an integrated probabilistic simulation	BIMprove Website
Business Logic of Digital Twin in BIMprove	BIMprove Website
Risk detection methodology for reducing accidents at construction sites!	BIMprove Website
Parameters to be monitored in construction sites, for reducing risks	BIMprove Website
BIMprove and Human-robot interaction	BIMprove Website
BIMprove and Usability	BIMprove Website
User Experience (UX) in BIMprove	BIMprove Website
The evolution of Digital Technologies in AECO industries	BIMprove Website
The BIMprove data architecture	BIMprove Website
Information sharing and data exchange in the AECO sector: BIMprove's approach	BIMprove Website
Usability and UX in mobile and XR applications	BIMprove Website
BIMprove as a major contributor towards using real-time digital twins in the AECO sector	BIMprove Website
Digital twins in the AECO sector	BIMprove Website
Requirements analysis and engineering in the AECO sector	BIMprove Website
Computer Vision Model Creation	BIMprove Website
Risk ontology for the construction industry	BIMprove Website
BIMprove's Risk Database	BIMprove Website
BIMprove Risk Object Visual Analysis System	BIMprove Website
Trends in technologies related to BIMprove	BIMprove Website
Accidents in the Construction Industry	BIMprove Website

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BIMprove Risk and Image Data Management Service	BIMprove Website
<u>The BIMprove Implementation Cycle</u>	BIMprove Website
How BIMproves merges IFC and data from reality to make its solution work	BIMprove Website
The BIMprove Concept	BIMprove Website
Digital Twin Lego Workshop at Construction City in Oslo	BIMprove Website
BIMprove travels to Oslo to work on the Scheduling and Cost Benefit Pilot Use Case	BIMprove Website
D2.3 "Open Interface Description for stationery, ground and UAV based data acquisition systems" is out!	BIMprove Website
BIMprove at ECCE 2022!	BIMprove Website
BIMprove's 4th Newsletter is out!	BIMprove Website
Project partners gather in Madrid to visit the Spanish Pilot Use Case	BIMprove Website
New family meeting with our sister projects on Digital Building Twins	BIMprove Website
BIMprove Onsite Technology Demonstration in Lausanne	BIMprove Website
BIMprove 5th Newsletter is out!	BIMprove Website
Meet the XR Viewer of BIMprove	BIMprove Website
CEN Workshop on 'Geometric framework, coordinate systems and markers for BIM construction projects'	BIMprove Website
EU SmartBuilt4EU D1.5 Smart Building EU Funded Innovations brochure	BIMprove Website
EU SmartBuilt4EU Brochure - Smart Buildings Future Technologies	BIMprove Website
Exploitation Workshop among 4 EU Digital Twin Innovation Projects	BIMprove Website
Mapping the AEC start-up ecosystem	BIMprove Website
Women in BIMprove: get to know Caroline Cheng	BIMprove Website
Women in BIMprove: get to know Ragnhild J. Eleftheriadis	BIMprove Website
Women in BIMprove: get to know Ingvild B. Småge Aursland	BIMprove Website
Stuttgart Integration Meeting: three days of collaboration and learning	BIMprove Website
BIMprove will be at BIM World Paris 2023!	BIMprove Website
BIMprove 6th Newsletter is out!	BIMprove Website
The European Commission publishes the Report 'Transition Pathway for Construction'	BIMprove Website
BIMprove at the World's Leading Trade Fair for Architecture, Materials, Systems – BAU 2023	BIMprove Website
BIMprove at BIM World Paris 2023: video presentation	BIMprove Website

Last Pilot Use Case visit at the Fyrstikkbakken construction site in Oslo	BIMprove Website
Calling for Stakeholder's feedback about BIMprove	BIMprove Website
BIMprove at BDTIC 2023: the Building Digital Twin International Congress!	BIMprove Website
BIMprove at the Digital Real Estate Summit 2023 Bilder	BIMprove Website
Deep Learning Machine Vision Solutions for Monitoring Safety Structures to Supplement Building Information Models	BIMprove Website
BIMprove at EU BIM 2023 in Valencia, the International BIM Congress	BIMprove Website
BIMprove participates at the Workshop to Explore the potentials of Digital Twin by Eura Construction	BIMprove Website
BIMprove celebrates its Final Review meeting in Lausanne, Switzerland	BIMprove Website
Deliverable 3.6 Benchmarking, Evaluation & Demonstration	BIMprove Website
Get to know the outstanding BIMprove results	BIMprove Website
Draft CWA: Position Markers for Digital Applications on Construction Sites, Structural Monitoring and BIM-Applications	BIMprove Website
BIMprove Last Newsletter is out!	BIMprove Website

3.4.3. Newsletters

During the project lifetime, newsletters acted as teasers to our work and summarise our main achievements. BIMprove has released a total of 7 Newsletter and contributed to 2 sister project's Newsletters. By the time of writing this deliverable, the project is preparing its contribution to a Flash Newsletter from the sister projects that will be launched at the end of August 2023.

Table 4: List of published Newsletters

Title	Link	Year
BIMprove 1st Newsletter	View	2021
BIMprove 2nd Newsletter	View	2021
BIMprove 3rd Newsletter	View	2021
BIMprove in the ASHVIN's Newsletter vol. 3	View	2022
BIMprove 4th Newsletter	View	2022
BIMprove in ASHVIN Newsletter vol. 4	View	2022
BIMprove 5th Newsletter	View	2022
BIMprove 6th Newsletter	View	2023
BIMprove 7th Newsletter	View	2023

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In BIMprove, we have used mailchimp as the email marketing tool. We have reached the final stage of the project with 77 subscribers and in the graphic below we share some metrics corresponding to the last 365 days, including the analytics regarding Newsletters 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th.

Figure 8: Newsletter metrics from the last 365 days

3.4.3.1.1 BIMprove's 1st Newsletter

Our 1st newsletter has been released in **June 2021**. It has been **distributed directly to 32 registered users**, and was been disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our first newsletter was read online by **46 people** and has been **downloaded 30 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

3.4.3.1.2 BIMprove's 2nd Newsletter

Similar to the above, our 2nd newsletter has been released in **December 2021**. It has been **distributed directly to 41 registered users**, and was disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our second newsletter was read online by **86 people** and has been **downloaded 24 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

3.4.3.1.3 BIMprove's 3rd Newsletter

Our 3rd newsletter has been released in **May 2022**. It has been **distributed directly to 46 registered users**, and was disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our second newsletter was read online by **77 people** and has been **downloaded 36 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

3.4.3.1.4 BIMprove's 4th Newsletter

Our 4th newsletter has been released in **October 2022**. It has been **distributed directly to 55 registered users**, and was disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our second newsletter was read online by **70 people** and has been **downloaded 24 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

3.4.3.1.5 BIMprove's 5th Newsletter

Our 5th newsletter has been released in **December 2022**. It has been **distributed directly to 58 registered users**, but has been disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our second newsletter was read online by **38 people** and has been **downloaded 19 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

For the 5th Newsletter, we prepared a 1-minute video summarising the highlights of 2022. The video received 42 visualisations so far.

Figure 9: BIMprove 2022 wrap-up: a year of achievements (video)

3.4.3.1.6 BIMprove's 6th Newsletter

Our 6th newsletter has been released in **March 2023**. It has been **distributed directly to 74 registered users**, and was disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our second newsletter was read online by **34 people** and has been **downloaded 19 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

3.4.3.1.7 BIMprove's 7th Newsletter

Our last newsletter has been released in **August 2023**. It has been **distributed directly to 78 registered users**, and has been disseminated through our social media as well. Overall, our second newsletter was read online by **30 people** and has been **downloaded 6 times**. It is publicly available through our [website](#).

3.4.4. Technical & Scientific (Peer Reviewed) Publications

As part of BIMprove research outcomes, the project has published a total of **10 peer-reviewed scientific research publications** in international journals or conferences, which have generated a total of **1198 number** of views and **597** number of downloads. In this section we outline all of them.

Title	BIMprove’s White paper on basic concepts of data integration services for building industry using BIM and Digital Building Twins		
Authors	Edvardsen, Dag; Ristin, Marko; Sziebig, Gabor; van de Venn, Hans Wernher		
Year	2021		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/4727840#.ZFuYAnZBy3A		
Abstract: This White Paper describes a proposal for a technology concept that will open the door to greater digitalisation within the construction sector, the core of which is a digital twin associated with a given building under construction. The proposal addresses the management of the highly heterogeneous environment inherent in the construction industry, and during the construction process in particular.			
No. Views	370	No. Downloads	237

Title	XR Based GUI Concept for BIM Digital Twin Data Visualization		
Authors	Kaj Helin; Vladimir Goriachev; Jaakko Karjalainen; Timo Kuula; Marja Liinasuo; Matthias Aust		
Year	2021		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/6044046#.ZG3bMHZBy3B		
Abstract: This extended abstract introduces the eXtended Reality (XR) based graphical user interface (GUI) concept for the construction of Digital Twin Model. The abstract also describes Augmented Reality (AR) tool called BIM@Construction, which is part of GUI concepts and visualizes digital twin data on a construction site.			
No. Views	92	No. Downloads	50

Title	Evaluation of BIMprove XR User Interfaces		
Authors	Matthias Aust; Melissa Otto; Julius Schippert; Jörg Frohnmayer; Kaj Helin; Marja Liinasuo; Timo Kuula		
Year	2022		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7198062#.ZG3bi3ZBy3B		

Abstract: This work documents the evaluation of the XR user interfaces introduced in Aust et al. 2021 and Helin et al. 2021 in the BIMprove project (BIMprove, 2022). It describes the procedures followed in the different tests with their results and suggests a pragmatic and cheap way to estimate the readiness of a collaborative software system for a specific context of use.

No. Views	120	No. Downloads	30
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Title	Storing, Maintaining & Updating the Digital Twin		
Authors	Ruprecht Altenburger; Dag Fjeld Edvardsen		
Year	2022		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7198266#.ZG3b3XZBy3B		
Abstract: Digital Twin technologies are making their way onto the construction site. In BIMprove, automated data collection systems are developed, the data processed and fed to Digital Twin in a clearly defined process. Next steps are to test, adapted and optimize the developed functionalities on 3 pilot construction sites. Clearly, adjustments will be necessary in the transition from the laboratory environment to the very specific conditions on construction sites.			
No. Views	83	No. Downloads	41

Title	BIM digital twin visualization in XR – Novel GUI concept		
Authors	Kaj Helin; Vladimir Goriachev; Jaakko Karjalainen; Timo Kuula; Marja Liinasuo; Matthias Aust		
Year	2022		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7198173#.ZG3cJnZBy3B		
Abstract: This extended abstract introduces the novel graphical user interface (GUI) concept for the visualization of Digital Twin Model in eXtended Reality (XR). The first version of the GUI concept has been introduced earlier (Helin et al., 2021). Based on the user evaluation of the BIMprove XR systems, the novel GUI has been updated. The abstract also describes BIM@Categories, which includes six (6) different GUIs to access Digital Twin Model. Work has been done in a European Commission funded H2020 project called “BIMprove - Improving Building Information Modelling by Realtime Tracing of Construction Processes” (BIMprove, 2022).			
No. Views	92	No. Downloads	54

Title	White Paper: Ontologies and Digital Building Twins (BIMprove contribution)		
Authors	Mads H. Rasmussen; Pieter Pauwels; María Poveda-Villalón; Sanju Tiwari; Raúl García-Castro; Pierre Bourreau; Bruno Fies; Jonas Sschlenger; Bruno Daniotti;		

	Seppo Törma; Mark Thomas; Michel Böhms; Gabor Sziebig; Angel Font; Eduard Loscos; Pablo Vicente-Legazpi; Peter Imbrechts		
Year	2022		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7342437#.ZG3cbXZBy3B		
Abstract: A review of existing ontologies in construction is presented (updated September 2022). Motivation, alignments and final applications with special interest on methodologies. Software Tools are presented in an Appendix. Some use cases are presented with different orientations. Final conclusions are oriented to new paths to follow in future developments, considering other technologies and commercial solutions nowadays. More than new ontologies the use of existing ontologies as DICON could help to standardize and make an ontologies map for construction possible. Progress with standards, as mentioned in a specific chapter about status of group CEN442 WG4, is essential to get a good level of interoperability, but it faces complex technical challenges. And the most sophisticated and perfect implementation sometimes means a non-practical approach, and too rigid to be used by the industry.			
No. Views	68	No. Downloads	55

Title	BIM@SiteOffice: Comparing IFC and point clouds in Multiuser VR – Workflows and Tools		
Authors	Jörg Frohnmayr; Frank Sulzmann; Matthias Aust; Jan-Filip Kvirgic; René Hellmuth; Cora Lenz		
Year	2022		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7198235#.ZG3crHZBy3B		
Abstract: The BIMprove (BIMprove 2022) system's goal is to enable Digital Twins in the construction phase by addressing two main challenges. The first challenge is combining information from the physical object with building information modeling (BIM) models in a precise overlay of as planned data versus as built data. Doing this requires combining BIM planning information with as-built data collected during the construction and switching from a georeferenced position to a local position to visualize this information in the BIM. As-built data is obtained with laser scans from robots and photogrammetry from day-ahead planned drone flights and is stored as point clouds inside the BIMprove system's backend. To create a reliable overlay, BIMprove's partners have come up with a marker-based solution in which physical markers on site and virtual ones in the BIM model are automatically detected and aligned.			
No. Views	101	No. Downloads	59

Title	Building’s digital twin model shown as first-person and third-person views		
Authors	M. Liinasuo; T. Kuula; V. Goriachev; K. Helin; M. Aust		
Year	2022		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7417624#.ZG3c_3ZBy3B		
Abstract: Construction industry is currently facing challenges such as a high number of occupational injuries and a somewhat weak connection between design and construction phases. One way to amend the situation is to increase data availability to construction professionals. Information about the structure and features of the building to be built should be shared so that various professionals can use the so-called digital twin model of the building for his/her purposes. We have created a concept for delivering the building information model (BIM) that can be viewed in various ways from various devices. We tested the viewing and using of BIM in augmented reality (AR), with high-end eXtended Reality (XR) technology (Microsoft HoloLens 2) and a tablet. Briefly, according to our test results, AR seems to be good when user needs to be perceived him/herself as if inside the building model, and tablet suits for viewing the digital model from the outside of it. Novice users of the AR technology need much more support in using the technology than the experienced ones. All test participants found the concept good and the technology with which to use it as promising.			
No. Views	57	No. Downloads	26

Title	Choosing between remote and face-to-face features in a test setting: methodology used in two usability and user experience case studies		
Authors	Marja Liinasuo; Timo Kuula; Vladimir Goriachev; Kaj Helin		
Year	2023		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7548582		
Abstract: Remote test settings have become more common due to COVID-19. This paper presents two user tests focusing on the usability and user experience of an augmented reality-related solution. We describe the proceeding of the tests from the perspective of what has been conducted face-to-face and remotely. Thereafter, the appropriateness of the used test methodology is evaluated based on (i) the acquired results, (ii) the ease of using and understanding the methods and (iii) the test atmosphere. The physical presence of a person providing technical support to the test participant proved vital for augmented reality-related testing; the location of other test organisers appears more indifferent. Finally, we present the perspectives to contemplate when choosing between face-to-face and remote features in the test setting.			
No. Views	60	No. Downloads	24

Title	Deep Learning Machine Vision Solutions for Monitoring Safety Structures to Supplement Building Information Models		
Authors	Tommi Aihkisalalo; Anu Purhonen; Ilkka Niskanen		
Year	2023		
Open Access	https://zenodo.org/record/7950278		
Abstract:	Building Information Models (BIM), provide a static view on building structures on design and construction time. During construction time, the safety structures and their positioning among conditions are vital for the safety of the employees on site. The models usually lack the temporospatial information regarding non-static safety structures as maintaining of such information manually is laborious. Thus, automated and continuous safety structure monitoring is costefficient and vital keeping the model up-to-date while improving construction site safety and risk information sharing among the construction related personnel during the project. This paper researches of providing up-to-date and supplementary safety structure information to building models by means of various deep learning-based machine vision solutions. The machine vision tasks consist of deep learning safety related object detection in images, point-clouds, and further instance segmentation to enable safety structure fitness determination by more traditional machine vision means.		
No. Views	155	No. Downloads	21

3.5. Events, Conferences and Workshops

BIMprove has participated in a number of scientific and technical events, conferences and workshops presenting our project activities, results and views related to the future of Digital Twins in Construction. Overall, we have participated in **37 events**.

Table 5: List of events, conferences and workshops

Event	Type	Date	Details
BIM FORUM 2020	Featured event	26/08/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
IEA HPT IoT Annex meeting	Featured event	21/10/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
The buildingSMART International Virtual Summit - 2020	Featured event	06/11/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIM Speed Industry Day	Workshop /Webinar	18/11/2020	Networking / Workshop

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BIM4Ren workshop	Workshop /Webinar	26/11/2020	Networking / Workshop
From BIM to Twin	Featured event	27/11/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIM supports digitalization of standards for the Construction sector	Featured event	15/12/2020	Networking
BIMprove at EUROVR 2020 International Conference!	Featured event	15/12/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
Digital Twin for Cities: Initiatives from around the world	Featured event	15/02/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
buildingSMART Norge faglig onsdag #12 (In Norwegian)	Featured event	10/03/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove project at BDTIC 2021	Featured event	17/03/2021	Networking/Webinar
BIMprove as part of the “Digital twins and integration of AI in construction industry” webinar	Featured event	27/05/2021	Networking/Webinar
BIMprove at Sustainable Places 2021	Featured event	15/07/2021	Networking/Webinar
BIMprove at CIB W78 - LDAC 2021	Workshop /Webinar	30/09/2021	Networking/Workshop
BIMprove at IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference!	Featured event	08/10/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)	Featured event	11/10/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at EUROXR 2021 International Conference!	Featured event	11/12/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at EURAD-PREDIS webinar!	Workshop /Webinar	01/01/2022	Networking /Webinar
BIMprove at Big Data Value Forum!	Featured event	05/01/2022	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at BDTIC 2022	Featured event	01/03/2022	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
World Building Congress 2022	Featured event	01/05/2022	Networking / Event

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Sustainable Places: Workshop Ontologies in Digital Twin	Featured event	30/06/2022	Networking/Workshop
BIMprove at EuroXR Stuttgart 2022	Featured event	08/09/2022	Networking/Event
Digital Twin Lego Workshop at Construction City in Oslo	Workshop /Webinar	15/09/2022	Workshop
BIMprove at ECCE 2022	Featured event	22/09/2022	Networking/Event
CEN Workshop session 1	Workshop /Webinar	03/02/2023	Networking/Workshop
Sister projects workshop on exploitation	Workshop /Webinar	06/02/2023	Networking/Workshop
BIMprove at the Digital Real Estate Summit 2023 Bilder	Featured event	08/03/2023	Networking/Event
CEN Workshop session 2	Workshop /Webinar	22/03/2023	Networking/Workshop
BIMprove at BIM World Paris 2023	Featured event	06/04/2023	Networking/Event
BIMprove at BAU 2023	Featured event	20/04/2023	Networking/Event
BIMprove at BDTIC 2023	Featured event	03/05/2023	Networking/Event
CEN Workshop session 3	Workshop /Webinar	12/05/2023	Workshop
EU BIM 2023 Valencia	Featured event	17/05/2023	Networking/Event
Digital Twin in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry. Workshop to Explore the potentials of Digital Twin	Featured event	05/06/2023	Networking/Event
CEN Workshop session 4	Workshop/Webinar	09/06/2023	Workshop
CEN Workshop Final Steps	Workshop/Webinar	22/08/2023	Workshop

In the context of community and networking, **BIMprove** partners have attended a number of events and webinars to which, even though **BIMprove** was not directly presented, we participated in the discussions for gaining useful knowledge that may be infused to the project and for networking purposes with other organisations and individuals. This “resource free” activity has brought considerable value to the project.

In this section we have chosen some of the main events to give more details about BIMprove participation and showcase its relevant contribution to the construction industry.

3.5.1. IEA HPT IoT Annex meeting

On **21 October 2020**, our project coordinator **SINTEF** gave a first overall presentation about the project and its intended activities in the IEA HPT IoT Annex meeting. That presentation took place in a small audience of 19 people and its intention was to provide an early overview of our project to a short but influential group of people. The project was very immature so no outcomes were presented, just an overview of the project.

Figure 10: IEA HPT IoT Annex meeting

3.5.2. BIMprove at EUROVR 2020

The **BIMprove** consortium is proud to have participated to the **EuroVR 2020**. Our partners [Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Engineering IAO](#) and [VTT](#) presented their innovative work related to **Multi User XR for Construction**, that takes place within our project. The 17th EuroVR International Conference – EuroVR 2020 – took place on **25-27 November 2020** in Valencia, Spain. The conference followed a series of successful European VR/AR conferences taking place since 2004 and known as INTUITION, JVRC and recently EuroVR (Bemen 2014, Lecco 2015, Athens 2016, Laval 2017, London 2018, and Tallinn 2019). The Immersive Neurotechnologies Lab (LabLENI) of the Polytechnic University of Valencia (UPV), Spain, is organizing the 2020 edition of this conference.

Figure 11: BIMprove at EuroXR 2021

Application Poster Honorary Mention Award

BIMprove user interfaces: Multi-user-XR for construction

Matthias Aust, Melissa Otto, and Kaj Helin

The presented poster entitled “**BIMprove User Interfaces: Multi-User-XR for Construction**”, introduces the idea of a multi-user, multi-device XR-system to be set up at a construction site, for both co-located and remote used and is available through our [public repository](#).

3.5.3. BDTIC 2021

On **27th of May 2021**, BIMprove participated in the first international event dedicated to **Building Digital Twins (BDTIC)** that was organised by the [Building Digital Twin Association](#). 17 speakers talked about new knowledge about BDT. The collaboration of world experts, who offered never-before-seen presentations on the situation of Building Digital Twin from NASA till the more advanced on-going European projects participated in the two sessions and the two keynote lectures. **The event has been viewed from over 500 people.**

Figure 12: BIMprove at BDTIC 2021

On behalf of **BIMprove**, our project coordinator [SINTEF Manufacturing](#) provided a presentation on “**Changing the rules of the construction: dynamic BIM models with DigitalTwin Technology**”. The presentation can be found [online here](#).

3.5.4. BIMprove as part of the “Digital twins and integration of AI in construction industry” webinar

On **July 15th 2021**, [Dr Gabor Szabig](#) from [SINTEF Manufacturing](#), represented **BIMprove**, at the “**Digital twins and integration of AI in construction industry**” webinar. The webinar was organized by the [Artificial Intelligence Research, Development and Innovation Network for Sustainable Cities](#) and was funded by the [Royal Academy of Engineering](#) under the [Frontiers Champion](#) award.

Figure 13: “Digital twins and integration of AI in construction industry” webinar

Dr Sziebig presented **BIMprove**'s objectives, technologies and innovations to a wide audience while the concept of digital twins and the integration of artificial intelligence in construction industry were discussed. You can watch the official recording of the event [from here](#).

3.5.5. BIMprove at EUROXR 2021

BIMprove project has participated in the [18th EuroXR](#) conference that took place in **Milan** (virtually), from the 24th to the 26th of November 2021, and was organized by [CNR-STIIMA](#), to support the competitiveness of the manufacturing sector through the innovation of factories and their production, enhancing human knowledge and innovation capacity.

3.5.6. 2021 IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)

BIMprove partners Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) and Catenda have presented an approach and a tool for collecting AECO-specific software requirements with the aim to foster reuse and leverage domain knowledge. Their scientific paper, **RASAECO: Requirements Analysis of Software for the AECO Industry**, has been published in the [Conference proceedings](#) while the source code for the tool can be found in our [public repository](#).

3.5.7. BIMprove at Sustainable Places 2021

BIMprove joined forces with [COGITO](#), [BIM2TWIN](#) and [ASHVIN](#) and organized a 120-minute hybrid workshop at the 9th annual edition of [Sustainable Places \(SP2021\)](#) on “[Digital Twin for the Construction Phase](#)“. The hybrid workshop took place on the **30th of September 2021**, discussing about the challenges of creating digital twin for the construction.

Figure 14: BIMprove at Sustainable Places 2021

The workshop was chaired by **Gabor Sziebig** from **SINTEF**, who is the coordinator of **BIMprove** project, while an opening statement was made by Ms Victoria Leroy from [European Health and Digital Executive Agency \(HaDEA\)](#).

3.5.8. BIMprove at CIB W78 - LDAC 2021

BIMprove project participated in the joint conference [CIB W78 – LDAC 2021](#) that took place in Luxembourg at **11-15 October 2021**. Our partner **HRS** set up a **BIMprove** corner, highlighting our project's recent development and goals and attracted interest on our activities. Our coordinator, SINTEF, participated in the [“Linking EU H2020 projects on digitization in the construction and maintenance industrys”](#) workshop, together with our H2020 sister projects [ASHVIN](#), [COGITO](#) and [BIM2TWIN](#) and representatives from [BIM4Ren](#), [BIM-SPEED](#), [BIMERR](#), [BIM4EEB](#), [SPHERE](#) and [CBIM](#), where the need of aligning effort when developing ontologies has been highlighted.

Figure 15: BIMprove at CIB W78 - LDAC 2021

3.5.9. Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2021

BIMprove project participated in the [European Big Data Value Forum 2021](#) that took place during **November 29 - December 3, 2021** | Ljubljana + Online, Slovenia. The European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) is the flagship event of the European Big Data and Data-Driven AI Research and Innovation community organised by the BDVA and the European Commission (DG CNECT). The EBDVF brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions in the areas of Data and AI. **BIMprove** presented itself in the [Data Driven Intelligent Digital Twins](#) session together with projects COGNITWIN, ILIAD, COGNIPLANT, FACTLOG and SIRIUS followed by a discussion on digital twin commonalities and differences for various domains. **The event has been viewed from 426 participants.**

Figure 16: European Big Data Value Forum 2021

3.5.10. BDTIC 2022

BIMProve project presented its achievements in the 2nd BDTIC international conference dedicated to Building Digital Twins, organised by the [Building Digital Twin Association](#).

The 2nd edition of the Building Digital International Congress at the CAATEEB on 26 May 2022. During the morning there were 4 workshops dedicated to: Ontology and Semantics, Privacy and Ethics Metrics, Real-Time Simulation and Artificial Intelligence, and Digital Twin Building.

Figure 17: Team members at the BDTIC 2022 Conference

3.5.11. World Building Congress 2022

BIMprove participated at the World Building Congress 2022 that took place during 27th June – 30th June, 2022 in Melbourne, Australia.

Our project coordinator Dr. Gabor Sziebig organised a special session addressing Building Digital Twins that focused on digital twins for the construction lifecycle phase of buildings.

Figure 18: Special Session Title: Building Digital Twins

100. Building's digital twin model shown as first-person and third-person views

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Construction industry is currently facing challenges, which should be met, because construction industry has declined in productivity. One means to amend the situation is related to data. There is a lot of data needed in the construction industry. However, not all data is presently available efficiently for construction professionals. Information about the structure and features of the building to be built should be shared so that various professionals can use the so-called digital twin model of the building for his/her purposes. We have created a concept for delivering the building information model (BIM) that can be viewed from the first-person and third-person perspectives. We tested the first-person and third-person views of BIM with high-end eXtended Reality (XR) technology (Microsoft HoloLens 2) and a tablet. Briefly, according to our test results, AR seems to be good for first-person immersive view, tablet suits for third-person view and novice users of the AR technology much more support in using the technology than the experienced ones. All test participants found the concept good and the technology with which to use it as promising.

3.5.12. Sustainable Places 2022: Workshop Ontologies in Digital Twin

BIMprove participated in the Sustainable Places Conference 2022 that took place in Nice, France. Our project representatives Gábor Sziebig and Wojciech Teclaw participated in the workshop: Ontologies in Digital Twin: Methodology, Lessons Learned and Practical Approach, which was co-organised by the Building Digital Twin Association (BDTA) and 6 EU-funded projects that develop a construction-phase digital-twin data model, and their ontological representation, capable of capturing all data requirements for the digital representation of building and/or infrastructure construction sites.

Figure 19: Sustainable Places 2022: Workshop Ontologies in Digital Twin

3.5.13. BDTIC 2023

On 3th May 2023, BIMprove project was present at the 3rd BDTIC International Congress dedicated to Building Digital Twins and organised by the Building Digital Twin Association.

Represented by our colleague Wojciech Teclaw from SINTEF, we had the opportunity to share BIMprove achievements and results to different stakeholders at The Beacon in Antwerp (Belgium). BIMprove participated in the workshop dedicated to Ontology and Semantics where Wojciech shared the work developed by the project on this matter enabling us to develop the BIMprove digital twin solution from a proven starting point, focusing on solving business problems.

Figure 20: Presentation at BDTIC 2023

3.5.14. EU BIM 2023 Valencia

The 12th edition of the International BIM Congress (EU BIM) took place in Valencia from Wednesday May 17 to Saturday May 20, 2023.

The BIMprove project was represented by our Valencian partner Robotnik who had the chance to join the BIM week full of workshops, presentations, BIM companies, BIM professionals and Master Class to expand the project networking opportunities. Our colleague Miguel Saura Herreros, Software and R&D Engineer, participated in a workshop addressing the use of point clouds in the construction phase, where he presented his experience of capturing reality in BIM projects, sharing BIMprove as a success case.

3.5.15. BIMprove at BIM World Paris 2023

BIM World is the key meeting place for BIM professionals and communities. Since 2015, BIM World has been the unmissable meeting place for professionals and communities for the uses of BIM and digital technology in the service of construction, real estate and urban development. The 2023 edition took place the 5 and 6 of April in Paris Expo, Porte de Versailles, and we were very excited that our team hosted a workshop during the second day of the event, led by our colleague Wojciech Teclaw, Research Scientist at SINTEF.

[Here](#) it is possible to watch the BIMprove presentation at the BIM World Paris 2023 by Wojciech Teclaw.

3.6. Activities Matrix

As already mentioned in previous subsections, most communication and dissemination activities served a two-fold purpose. The matrix below summarises under which phase (either communication or dissemination) each group of activities falls. It also provides the stakeholder target groups) that each activity was targeted for. It is important to mention that this matrix depicts only the activities that took place during these first 18 months and does not refer to future activities.

Activity	Communication			Dissemination			Stakeholders
	Plan & revisit	Early bird Communication	Targeted Communication	Analysis	Increase impact	Adoption	
Digital Tools	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	All
Key Collaborations	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	Construction Industry, H2020 Funded Projects, Digital Twin Tech Providers
Online Articles & Newsletters	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	All
Publications	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	Construction Industry, H2020 Funded Projects, Policy Makers, Digital Twin Tech Providers, Digital Transformation Advocates
Events, Conferences & Workshops	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	Construction Industry, H2020 Funded Projects, Digital Twin Tech Providers, Digital Transformation Advocates

4. KPIS FINAL STATUS

For **BIMprove** it has been very important to continuously monitor our KPIs. Even though some KPIs were quite optimistic and affected by the COVID-19 challenges, we managed to remain on track. As the project became more mature and could reveal more tangible and presentable results, our efforts have lean towards emphasising on dissemination and increasing of key performance indicators.

Table 6: BIMprove final KPIs

Measure	Indicator	Target	Status M36
Peer-reviewed Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific research publications in international journals / conferences	10	10
	Non-scientific publications (articles, blog posts, news pieces...)	10	47
Publications	Scientific and Technical Publications (e.g., articles, blog posts) (yearly)	20	25
Events	No. of scientific events participated	30	25
	No. of non-scientific events participated	10	11
Project Website	No. of visitors (total)	1,000	4,782
Printed Material	No. of hard copies (e.g. flyers) distributed	2,000	+2,000
Social Media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	3,000	3,166
	No. of impressions (monthly average)	500	5,928
Videos	No. of videos produced	3	31
	No. of visits (by the end of the project)	3,000	3,651
Newsletters	No. of newsletters contributed/released	9	9

5. AGILE STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT STRATEGY: EVALUATION OF THE STRATEGY

5.1. Methodology

In parallel with the communication and dissemination activities, **BIMprove** consortium applied its novel approach on agile stakeholder management. A strategy that has been described in in [D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan](#) and aimed to establish a two-way information stream with specific organisations and initiatives, in order to not only inform them about our project, but also receive feedback, opinions and insights to be infused in the project’s future work. The framework followed an iterative implementation structure based on **Sprints**, time-boxes of 6 months where the main goal is to incrementally increase and reinforce the engagement of the stakeholders with the initiative.

During the first 18 Months of the project, **BIMprove** consortium has implemented 3 Sprints. Each Sprint had a specific focus on some organisations and stakeholder groups. For strategic purposes and because of the nature of this current deliverable (public) certain information cannot be disclosed. However, a synopsis of each Sprint with information regarding specific target groups, nature of interactions and key learnings are presented in the following tables.

Table 7: Sprint Q1

Sprint Q1 (M01-M06)		
Phase 1 Scouting	Phase 2 Interaction	Phase 3 Learning
H2020 Funded Projects • LC-EEB-02-2018	Participation and Networking with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM Speed - Industry Day • BIM4Ren - workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating synergies with other H2020 projects that were funded by previous calls, is quite valuable as they might have performed work that could be important for recently funded projects. • Have an early start on standardisation with key organisations becomes a valuable guideline for future activities. • It's very important to find the right persons from organisations and associations you wish to contact.
Digital Twin Tech Providers	Participation and Networking with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN/CENELC - BIM supports digitalization of standards for the Construction sector 	

Table 8: Sprint Q2

Sprint Q2 (M07-M12)		
Phase 1 Scouting	Phase 2 Interaction	Phase 3 Learning

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<p>H2020 Funded Projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LC-EEB-08-2020 • Standardisation related initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formulate a cluster with ASHVIN, COGITO, BIM2TWIN • Sign MoU with StandICT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligning efforts with initiatives funded under the same call in critical – it amplifies the influence of all projects and magnifies available resources. • Establish an Advisory Board with high-profile people, with extensive know how on project's topic of interest allow a valuable input stream of knowledge. • Make sure what kind of IP you expose to the community. • By involving ETPs and other influential associations and industrial players and end users into a wider project's ecosystem allows the project to receive valuable insights and feedback. Presentations and unstructured discussions provided the project with fruitful insights that assisted us on better shaping our concept and make it more attractive and valuable to them. • One-to-one discussion with key players are a good way for collecting feedback. • Make sure that the project is mature enough when discussion with potential end users.
<p>Digital Twin Tech Providers</p>	<p>Invite member to our Advisory Board from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dublin City University • TU Dortmund • Monash University • University of Central Lancashire 	
<p>Construction Industry Digital Transformation Advocates</p>	<p>Invite member to our Advisory Board from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ManuFuture-EU ETP • EU-Robotics Aisbl ETP • buildingSMART Switzerland <p>Present our project to industrial players:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IBM • Shirley Parsons • NCC • CERVVAL • PlanB • SBP 	

Table 9: Sprint Q3

Sprint Q3 (M13-M18)		
Phase 1 Scouting	Phase 2 Interaction	Phase 3 Learning
<p>H2020 Funded Projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LC-EEB-02-2018 • LC-EEB-08-2020 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Host a joint workshop with COGITO, BIM2TWIN and ASHVIN at the 9th annual edition of Sustainable Places (SP2021) on "Digital Twin for the Construction Phase". • Participate in a joint workshops with BIM4Ren, BIM-SPEED, BIMERR, BIM4EEB, SPHERE at CIB W78 – LDAC 2021 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing joint initiatives and activities with other projects give the opportunity to actively learn from each other and gives room for new ideas and concepts to be generated and exchanged on the fly. • Exposing project developments to end users through a physical interaction gives the opportunity to gather feedback and trigger interest. • Having an exploitation plan (or market uptake plan/business model) in place, is crucial when you talk with end users as they could be interested on ways of using your solution.
<p>Construction Industry Digital Twin Tech Providers</p>	<p>Set up a BIMprove corner to interact with Construction Industry Players and Digital Twin Tech Providers</p>	

Our first 3 Sprints were quite successful as we managed to interact and gather feedback from a number of organisations and initiatives both in a structured and unstructured way. Even though most of the feedback we received is confidential, any valuable insight that we felt as useful and relevant to our work has been infused to our current and future work and will be reflected in our outcomes.

During the second half of the project, **BIMprove** consortium has implemented additional Sprints focusing on increasing impact and awareness. **As regards to the scouting phase** we have kept connecting with new stakeholders, for instance, we have established collaboration with Horizon Europe projects such as Reincarnate, HumanTech and Reconmatic.

Concerning the interaction phase, we have increased the number of peer-reviewed publications, the participation in events and conferences, the publication of articles and the development of engaging campaigns. We have organised a set of CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) meetings to develop a pre-standard which is valid for up to six years with the aim to serve as a basis for a full standard. At the beginning of May 2023, we launched a survey inviting relevant stakeholders, including construction industry organisations, digital twin tech providers, BIM experts, other EU funded projects, digital transformation advocates and policy makers to provide their feedback on the BIMprove project. BIMprove has developed a robust result campaign showcasing with different resources (articles, publications, videos, social media activity) the outcomes of the project. Regarding exploitation, we have organised several meetings addressing the future of the project.

As a result, we have published the draft CWA “Position markers for digital applications on construction sites, structural monitoring and BIM-applications”. The final version will be presented to the public for consultation and comment and its final version published in autumn 2023. We have received seven replies to the survey coming from the following experts: BIM Technician, Research Group Director, Sustainability Manager, Managing Director, Senior Researcher and Innovation & Technology Advice, providing high quality feedback. The result campaign is raising awareness about BIMprove functionalities and we can see that especially in the social media metrics. As an outcome, we are in the process of developing The BIMprove Alliance and analysing future project opportunities to give continuity to the work carried out.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has provided a list of the main dissemination and communication activities carried out during the project duration and has described the approach, actions, materials and strategies used for external communication, along with the engagement and uptake of the results by relevant stakeholders.

Dissemination activities and events have been carefully planned and defined in the scope of the Impact Master Plan (Deliverable D4.1) which was used as an initial strategy further updated and reviewed on a regular basis during the lifetime of the project. The results of the activities of Work Package 4 and the impact achieved have been monitored by the work package leader (AUSTRALO) with the support of all project partners.

Dissemination included a wide range of traditional information channels, such as project brochure, newsletters, social media posts and publication of news regarding the project, but also through the partners' own channels, in order to inform all kind of stakeholders interested in the digitalisation of the construction industry sector.

The BIMprove website was designed to be evolutive and dynamic, and all documents and deliverables published by the project partners have been or will be soon made available for download.

BIMprove was presented in major international industry events, in in connection with other construction related EU initiatives. A significant number of papers were published during the project lifetime.

A large audience has been reached by BIMprove and the project has at the same time ensured a proper dissemination towards the Future of Construction to ensure a smooth and effective transfer of results into related projects.

In conclusion, the Communication and Dissemination Plan has been implemented according to the plan, meeting most of the important indicators, even exceeding in some cases the initially planned. BIMprove partners are willing to continue disseminating the project results beyond the project lifetime to ensure better sustainability and usability of the project results.